

BARBITURATES. PART I. 5:5-DIETHYL- N^1 -(SUBSTITUTED BENZYL)
AND N^1 -(SUBSTITUTED PHENYL) BARBITURATES AND
THIOBARBITURATES

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Several N^1 -substituted benzyl-5:5-diethyl barbiturates and thiobarbiturates have been prepared and described.

Barbiturates have been studied very extensively. 5:5-Diethyl barbiturate, Veronal, was the first barbiturate used as a hypnotic (Fischer and Von Mering, *Therap. Gegenwart.*, 1903, 44, 97). 5-Ethyl-5-phenyl barbiturate, Luminal, was introduced as an anticonvulsant by Hauptman (*Munch. med. Wochschr.*, 1912, 59, 1907) in the treatment of epilepsy. 5-Ethyl-5-(1-methylbutyl)-2-thiobarbituric acid, Pentothal, and 5-ethyl-5-isoamyl-2-thiobarbituric acid, Thioethamyl, are useful as general anesthetics (Volwiller, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 1961). Kushner *et al.* (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1951, 16, 1283) found Hibicon, *N*-benzyl- β -chloropropionamide, useful in grand mal epilepsy. N^1 -alkylation of barbiturates makes them more useful in epileptic conditions. Mebaral, 1-methyl-5-ethyl-5-phenyl barbiturate, is an useful anticonvulsant. *N*-alkyl derivatives of substituted succinimides have also been found to exhibit anticonvulsant properties (Miller *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4895; 1953, 75, 6256).

It was considered of interest to synthesise barbiturates containing substituted benzyl group on the nitrogen atom. 5:5-Diethyl- N^1 -(substituted benzyl) barbiturates and thiobarbiturates have been synthesised and described in the present communication. For comparison some N^1 -substituted-phenyl thiobarbiturates have also been prepared.

Barbiturates were synthesised by the condensation of diethyl ethylmalonate and the substituted benzylureas and thioureas in presence of sodium ethoxide.

EXPERIMENTAL

Substituted benzylureas were prepared from the corresponding amines and potassium cyanate in presence of an acid. The hitherto-unknown substituted benzylureas are shown in Table I. Substituted benzylthioureas were prepared as described previously (Shah, Trivedi and Trivedi, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 423; Trivedi and Trivedi, *ibid.*, 1958, 35, 657). Diethyl ethylmalonate was prepared by the standard method (Wallingford and Jones, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 578).

Condensation of Diethyl Ethylmalonate with Substituted Ureas and Thioureas.—To a solution of sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (0.2 g. atom) and absolute ethanol (70 c.c.), was quickly added, with shaking, diethyl ethylmalonate (0.05 *M*), followed by appropriate substituted urea (0.05 *M*) or thiourea (0.06 *M*). The reaction mixture was then refluxed at 120° for 8 to 10 hours, the excess of alcohol distilled off, and the mixture diluted with 100 to 120 c.c. of water. It was filtered off and the filtrate after acidifying and keeping overnight deposited the barbituric acids. These were crystallised from alcohol or benzene; yield 25 to 30%.

N^1 -(Substituted benzyl)-5:5-diethyl barbiturates, thus prepared, are shown in Table II. N^1 -(Substituted benzyl)-5:5-diethylthiobarbituric acids prepared are shown in Table III and N^1 -substituted phenyl- λ -thiobarbituric acids are shown in Table IV.

TABLE I

Substituted benzylureas.

Compound.		M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
X=	R=			Found.	Calc.
<i>o</i> -Cl	H	143°	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{ON}_2\text{Cl}$	15.1	15.2
<i>p</i> -Cl	H	122°	"	12.1	"
<i>o</i> -Br	H	162°	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{ON}_2\text{Br}$	12.2	12.2
<i>p</i> -Br	H	172°	"	12.2	"
2 Me (3:4)	H	164°	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{ON}_2$	15.6	15.7
2 Me (2:5)	H	196°	"	15.7	"
<i>m</i> -OMe	H	148°	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$	15.5	15.6
H	Et	104°	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{ON}_2$	15.7	15.7
H	<i>n</i> -Pr	116°	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{16}\text{ON}_2$	14.5	14.6

TABLE II

 N^1 -(Substituted benzyl)-5:5-diethylbarbituric acids.

Compound.		M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
X=	R=			Found.	Calc.
<i>o</i> -Cl	H	248°	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2\text{Cl}$	9.0	9.1
<i>p</i> -Cl	H	134°	"	9.0	"
<i>o</i> -Br	H	120-21°	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2\text{Br}$	7.9	7.9
<i>m</i> -Br	H	120°	"	7.9	"
<i>p</i> -Br	H	124°	"	7.9	"
<i>o</i> -Me	H	120°	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$	9.7	9.7
<i>m</i> -Me	H	106°	"	9.7	"
<i>p</i> -Me	H	117°	"	9.7	"
2 Me (3:4)	H	178°	"	9.1	9.3
2 Me (2:4)	H	136°	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$	9.2	"
2 Me (2:5)	H	267°	"	9.2	"
<i>o</i> -OMe	H	132-33°	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$	9.2	9.2
<i>m</i> -OMe	H	Wax-like	"	9.2	9.2
<i>p</i> -OMe	H	224-25°	"	9.2	9.2
H	Me	90°	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$	9.6	9.7
H	Et	109°	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$	9.2	9.3
H	<i>n</i> -Pr	88°	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$	8.8	8.9

The two following phenylthioureas used for the preparation of N^1 -(substituted phenyl)-2-thiobarbituric acids seem to be hitherto unknown.

p-*n*-Butoxyphenylthiourea, m.p. 158°. (Found: S, 14.1. $C_{11}H_{16}ON_2S$ requires S, 14.3%).

p-*n*-Hexyloxyphenylthiourea, m.p. 112°. (Found: S, 12.6. $C_{13}H_{20}ON_2S$ requires S, 12.7%).

TABLE III

N^1 -(Substituted benzyl)-5:5-diethyl-2-thiobarbituric acids.

Compound.		M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
X =	R			Found.	Calc.
<i>o</i> -Cl	H	114°	$C_{15}H_{17}O_2N_2ClS$	8.6	8.6
<i>m</i> -Cl	H	118°	"	8.6	"
<i>p</i> -Cl	H	120°	"	8.5	"
<i>o</i> -Br	H	116°	$C_{15}H_{17}O_2N_2BrS$	7.5	7.6
<i>m</i> -Br	H	122°	"	7.5	"
<i>p</i> -Br	H	142°	"	7.5	"
<i>o</i> -Me	H	112-14°	$C_{16}H_{20}O_2N_2S$	9.1	9.2
<i>m</i> -Me	H	92°	"	9.2	"
<i>p</i> -Me	H	163°	"	9.2	"
2 Me (3:4)	H	179-80°	$C_{17}H_{22}O_2N_2S$	8.7	8.8
2 Me (2:4)	H	118°	"	8.7	"
2 Me (2:5)	H	116°	"	8.8	"
<i>o</i> -OMe	H	112°	$C_{16}H_{20}O_3N_2S$	8.7	8.8
<i>m</i> -OMe	H	117-18°	"	8.7	"
<i>p</i> -OMe	H	127-28°	"	8.7	"
H	Me	120°	$C_{16}H_{20}O_2N_2S$	9.2	9.2
H	Et	110°	$C_{17}H_{22}O_2N_2S$	8.8	8.8
H	<i>n</i> -Pr	112°	$C_{18}H_{24}O_2N_2S$	8.4	8.4

TABLE IV

5:5-Diethyl-N¹-(substituted phenyl)-2-thiobarbituric acids.

Compound.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Calc.
X =				
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	216°	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₂ S	10.3	10.3
<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	200°	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₂ S	9.8	9.8
<i>p</i> - <i>n</i> -OC ₃ H ₇	120°	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₂ S	9.3	9.4
<i>p</i> - <i>n</i> -OC ₄ H ₉	115°	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₂ S	8.9	8.9
<i>p</i> - <i>n</i> -OC ₅ H ₁₁	116°	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₂ S	8.5	8.6
<i>p</i> - <i>n</i> -OC ₆ H ₁₃	130°	C ₂₀ H ₂₈ O ₃ N ₂ S	8.2	8.2
<i>o</i> -Cl	121°	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₂ ClS	9.0	9.0
<i>m</i> -Cl	183°	"	"	"
<i>p</i> -Cl	212°	"	"	"
<i>m</i> -Br	115°	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₂ BrS	7.8	7.9
<i>p</i> -Br	246°	"	"	"

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